

Microscopic and transcriptome analyses of early colonization of tomato roots by *Trichoderma harzianum*

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Summary. The capacity of the fungus *Trichoderma harzianum* CECT 2413 to colonize roots and stimulate plant growth was analyzed. Tobacco seedlings (*Nicotiana benthamiana*) transferred to Petri dishes inoculated with *T. harzianum* conidia showed increased plant fresh weight (140%) and foliar area (300%), as well as the proliferation of secondary roots (300%) and true leaves (140%). The interaction between strain CECT 2413 and the tomato-root system was also studied during the early stages of root colonization by the fungus. When *T. harzianum* conidia were inoculated into the liquid medium of hydroponically grown tomato plants (*Lycopersicon esculentum*), profuse adhesion of hyphae to the plant roots as well as colonization of the root epidermis and cortex were observed. Confocal microscopy of a *T. harzianum* transformant that expressed the green fluorescent protein (GFP) revealed intercellular hyphal growth and the formation of plant-induced papilla-like hyphal tips. Analysis of the *T. harzianum*-tomato interaction in soil indicated that the contact between *T. harzianum* and the roots persisted over a long period of time. This interaction was characterized by the presence of yeast-like cells, a novel and previously undescribed developmental change. To study the molecular mechanism underlying fungal ability to colonize the tomato-root system, the *T. harzianum* transcriptome was analyzed during the early stages of the plant-fungus interaction. The expression of fungal genes related to redox reactions, lipid metabolism, detoxification, and sugar or amino-acid transport increased when *T. harzianum* colonized tomato roots. These observations are similar to those regarding the interactions of mycorrhiza and pathogenic fungi with plants. [Int Microbiol 2007; 10(1):19-27]

Key words: *Trichoderma harzianum* · plant-fungus interaction · tomato · tobacco · mycorrhiza · gene expression

Introduction

The fungal genus *Trichoderma* is cosmopolitan in soils, and the ecological adaptability of *Trichoderma* species is evidenced by their widespread distribution, including under different environmental conditions and on various substrates.

This physiological flexibility together with the antagonistic action of *Trichoderma* spp. against phytopathogenic fungi and the ability of these fungi to promote plant growth have made them attractive biological control agents [14]. The ability of *Trichoderma* to recognize and parasitize phytopathogenic fungi in the rhizosphere [4,11,26,40] has been ascribed to several complex mechanisms, such as nutrient competition, antibiosis, mycoparasitism, induction of systemic resistance, and increased plant-nutrient availability [21,28,37].

Species of the *Trichoderma* genus are characteristically saprophytes [14]; however, root colonization by some *Trichoderma* strains is a common phenomenon in the field [11]. The relationship between *Trichoderma* and plants has

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